

Beyond the Battlefield: The War in Ukraine and its Protracted Impact on Human and Labor Rights. Detailed Analysis of Crimes Against Humanity in the Context of Human Capital Management (2014-2023)

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RESUMEN

The aim of the article was to describe the key historical events in Ukraine, during the period 2014-2023, which are involved in crimes against humanity (crimes against humanity) and national security as a result of military actions of Russia. In addition, for convenience, the historical analysis is divided before and after the full-scale invasion (2022-2023). The scientific task was to present a historical and critical point of view on the crimes against humanity that have been committed in Ukraine within the framework of the events of the last nine years. At the same time, the methodology of the research passed through the use of the method of historical analysis and hermeneutics. As a result of the study, the historical determinants reflecting the state of crimes against humanity and national security of Ukraine were identified, with special emphasis on the events in the east of the country and the Crimean Peninsula. It is concluded that in such conditions the system of human resource management in Ukraine suffers greatly. It is established that mass migration, loss of human resources, civilian casualties and destruction of infrastructure took place during the last nine years of the war.

Keywords: human rights; crimes against humanity; war in Ukraine; national security; war history.

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Más allá del Campo de Batalla: La Guerra en Ucrania y su Prolongado Impacto en los Derechos Humanos y Laborales. Análisis detallado de los crímenes de lesa humanidad en el contexto de la gestión del capital humano (2014-2023)

RESUMEN

El objetivo del artículo fue describir los acontecimientos históricos clave en Ucrania, durante el período 2014-2023, que están involucrados en crímenes contra la humanidad (crímenes de lesa humanidad) y la seguridad nacional como resultado de acciones militares de Rusia. Además, por conveniencia, el análisis histórico se divide antes y después de la invasión a gran escala (2022-2023). La tarea científica fue presentar un punto de vista histórico y crítico sobre los crímenes contra la humanidad que se han cometido en Ucrania en el marco de los acontecimientos de los últimos nueve años. Al mismo tiempo, la metodología de la investigación paso por el uso del método de análisis histórico y la hermenéutica. Como consecuencia del estudio, se identificaron los determinantes históricos que reflejan el estado de los crímenes contra la humanidad y la seguridad nacional de Ucrania, con especial énfasis en los acontecimientos en el este del país y la península de Crimea. Se concluye que en tales condiciones el sistema de gestión de recursos humanos de Ucrania sufre mucho. Se ha establecido que la migración masiva, la pérdida de recursos humanos, las víctimas civiles y la destrucción de infraestructura tuvieron lugar durante los últimos nueve años de la guerra.

Palabras clave: derechos humanos; crímenes de lesa humanidad; guerra en Ucrania; seguridad nacional; historia de la guerra.

Introduction

The issue of the protection of human rights in the context of the global fight against crimes against the civilian population and the protection of Ukraine's national security, within its officially recognized borders, is of paramount importance in the modern world, and is becoming a basic requirement for the consolidation of a civilized and progressive society, in accordance with the postulates of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, which proclaim in Article 1: "All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights and, endowed as they are with reason and conscience, should behave towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood."

Humanity, which has already experienced two world wars in the 20th century, as well as numerous smaller military conflicts, has globally recognized the key value of human rights as universal principles aimed at preserving the inviolability of human dignity, freedom of thought and equality. An example of the international recognition of the transcendental value of human rights was the postulation by the United Nations in 1948 of the General Declaration of Human Rights. The adoption of this Declaration is definitely proof of a global commitment to the inflexibility of the right of every person to life, the safeguarding of his or her dignity and equality before the law, regardless of his or her social status, ethnicity or religion.

Respect for human rights is important for several reasons. First, respect for fundamental rights is a guarantee of the maintenance of social stability and peace in general. Whereas the violation of these rights may be a trend or appear as a consequence of social problems,

conflicts and military actions. Second, strict observance of human rights is an important factor in society's resistance to growing political, economic and other problems. This is especially true today, when the world is increasingly confronted with numerous destabilizing factors that can directly impact the dignity of the human person or other forms of life.

A commitment to human rights helps to mitigate these challenges, fostering an environment in which dialogue and understanding can thrive above conflict and division. For consolidated democracies in the 21st century, combating crimes against humanity is crucial not only for the sake of global justice, but also to prevent future atrocities such as genocide, terrorism or war. History has shown that impunity for such crimes often leads to their repetition, as perpetrators of atrocities feel emboldened and victims feel abandoned by the international community.

The creation of international tribunals and the International Criminal Court created by the Rome Statute of 1998 reflects the collective effort to hold individuals and States accountable for serious crimes and deter potential perpetrators. This is increasingly important in an era in which conflicts and humanitarian crises are often relayed in real time through social media, including so-called social networks, highlighting the urgent need for effective institutional mechanisms to address these violations in a forceful manner.

In the context of ensuring Ukraine's national security, the issues of protection of human rights and combating crimes against humanity are key and decisive. Respect for these rights is the main condition for stability and safe functioning of any civilized country. The modern understanding of national security includes not only the protection of territorial states within their geographical borders and the fight against negative factors and external threats, but also the implementation of measures aimed at protecting individual citizens from internal threats, including terrorism, organized crime and official abuses. At the same time, it is of vital importance to maintain an optimal balance between trying to organize the full protection of national interests and ensuring the inviolability of human rights when implementing these measures.

In times of globalization, the protection of human rights and the fight against crimes against humanity go far beyond the borders of a State. Powerful economic, social and digital relations between countries have led to a situation where a normal country, i.e. one that is not a technological and military power, is often unable to solve the problem of protecting its own interests. This applies to such problems as cybercrime, human trafficking, international terrorism and others. At the same time, effective and synergistic activities of several states and global organizations such as the North Atlantic Treaty Organization NATO or the European Union EU can ensure a high level of national security for each of the participants in this process.

Within the general framework of the defense of human rights, labor rights are often less recognized than political rights or civil liberties, since it is through work that people and communities dignify their lives, contribute to social development and spend most of their time. In fact, Article 23 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that:

1. Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favorable conditions of work and to protection against unemployment.
2. Everyone, without any discrimination whatsoever, has the right to equal pay for equal work.
3. Everyone who works has the right to just and favorable remuneration ensuring for himself and his family an existence worthy of human dignity, and supplemented, if necessary, by other means of social protection.
4. Everyone has the right to form and to join trade unions for the protection of his interests (United Nations General Assembly, 1948).

Bolton (2010) establishes a foundational view on the dignity of work, arguing that recognizing the inherent value of work is essential to creating a meaningful connection between individuals and their work. This perspective is not only crucial for personal fulfillment, but also serves as a defense against exploitation and dehumanization that can escalate into crimes against humanity within the workplace.

Broadening the theoretical discussion, Brantley, Nicolini, and Kirkhart (2021) call for a reevaluation of conventional narratives surrounding the human rights story within social work education. They advocate for an intersectional approach that recognizes the complex ways in which human rights abuses, including those related to work and employment, intersect with diverse social identities. This approach is vital for human resource management systems that seek to protect against discrimination and uphold the rights of all workers.

For their part, Frey and MacNaughton (2016) highlight the importance of applying a human rights perspective to achieve full employment and decent work, as outlined in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. They argue that the incorporation of human rights perspectives is essential to guide policies and practices towards these goals, underlining the role of human resource management systems in actualizing these principles.

Gozdecka (2021) explores the sustainability of the healthcare sector during the COVID-19 pandemic, demonstrating possible scenarios of how national security issues may affect human rights in the workplace, including employment issues and safe labor relations. Thus, the author of the study points out the importance of organizing an effective human resource management system in the context of maintaining a balance between the health and safety of workers in the workplace in crisis and emergency situations.

Similarly, Greer and Sokol (2014) explore how current European Union EU legislation affects health and social justice workers, highlighting the limits and legal framework of current measures to protect these rights. The results of this study provide insight into how to most effectively adapt modern EU legal standards to human resource management systems and, at the same time, organize employment policies that meet modern human rights standards.

The historical context of human rights is examined in Lamb's (2019) study. With the help of this scholarly article, there is a broader opportunity to analyze the percolations of contem-

porary problems in this area, in particular, the issues of crimes against humanity and crimes against the sovereignty of individual countries.

Similarly, Park, Murdie, and Davis (2019) contribute to the understanding of human rights advocacy by offering a dynamic perspective on how human rights issues relevant to HRM emerge and evolve over time. This viewpoint underscores the importance of adaptive and proactive HRM systems to respond to changing human rights concerns. For his part, Tapiola (2021) addresses international labor standards and human rights at work, highlighting the global governance structures that influence HRM practices. This emphasis on international cooperation and standards orients HRM systems towards more humane practices and respect for fundamental rights.

Wettstein (2020) examines the relationship between historical origins and modern business principles in the context of respect for human rights. In this case, particular attention is paid to corporate social responsibility standards. This study is key to understanding the historical path towards the creation of the human resource management system and its evolution in the context of respecting human rights and ensuring social equality.

In addition, this study constitutes a certain methodological basis for the effective integration of human rights observance mechanisms in the workplace, in the context of challenges and threats, updating the struggle of companies against crimes against humanity. A study by Zolka et al., (2021) discusses the limitations of human rights in times of COVID-19. In particular, it refers to the issue of restriction of the right of movement. The authors offer their interpretation of the problem and possible ways to solve it. Thus, the study proposes a number of measures to create a flexible system of human resources management with the development of digital sources of communication.

Taken together, these papers present a multifaceted view of the challenges and opportunities of integrating human rights principles into human resource management systems, especially in contexts of protecting against crimes against humanity and ensuring national security in Ukraine. Beyond their particularities, the cited authors advocate a nuanced and interdisciplinary approach that takes into account the dignity of labor, the complexity of social and global challenges and the evolving nature of human rights advocacy in specific contexts.

For Ukraine, the issue of human rights protection became relevant in 2014, with the onset of major political, military, economic and social upheavals. Starting with the development of the Euromaidan protests in late 2013, when organized citizens expressed their discontent with the then government's decision to abandon the path of European integration and push for democratization of society in favor of maintaining relations with Russia.

Thus, in 2014, Ukraine faced the phenomenon of an active societal struggle for sovereignty and democratic governance. The situation worsened markedly when Russia annexed

Crimea in March 2014, and initiated an illegitimate military conflict in eastern Ukraine, which resulted in widespread human rights violations including illegal population movements, the deaths of thousands of people, and abuses of power by the occupying authorities, all of which have been widely documented.

The annexation of Crimea and the conflict in the Donbas region have not only represented a direct challenge to Ukraine's sovereignty and territorial integrity, but have also created a humanitarian crisis. The fighting has caused thousands of deaths and injuries, and millions of people have been displaced from their homes. These events have raised serious concerns about violations of international humanitarian law, including allegations of war crimes, crimes against humanity and ethnic discrimination, among others.

The need for accountability and justice is paramount in addressing these violations, as impunity could set a dangerous precedent not only for Ukraine, but for the existing international order. The response of the international community, including sanctions against Russia and support for Ukraine, reflects the overall importance of upholding human rights and international law in the 21st century. In addition, the situation has highlighted the critical role of international and non-governmental organizations in documenting abuses and providing humanitarian aid, underscoring the global nature of human rights advocacy.

1. Methodology

In the arduous process of conducting the research we used the method of historical analysis and hermeneutics. The synthesis of these methods was decisive for the success of the research. This is because, while historical analysis provides the ability to structure complex chronological sequences, hermeneutics provides the tools to decipher these events in detail and interpret them in such a way as to obtain the conclusions most in line with historical reality. This dualistic or hybrid approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of the historical origins and consequences of the events in Ukraine, as well as identifying the nature of the resulting crimes against humanity and human rights violations.

At the same time, a detailed analysis of the events also opens up the possibility of finding ways to solve a number of problems related to human rights violations, as well as to optimize the modern HR management system. Using these methods in the research process, not only an analysis of past events was carried out, but also the possible consequences and prospects of future activities of the HR management system were formulated in the context of respect for human rights.

Thus, the combined use of historical analysis and hermeneutics in our study served to conduct a detailed and critical analysis of a single period of contemporary Ukrainian history, in order to contribute to a broader understanding of conflicts and their impact on human development and peculiarities of respect for human rights even in the most crisis situations (Fig. 01).

Figure 1. Main methods used in our article.

Source: Own elaboration.

In general, the method of historical analysis is employed to systematically review and interpret the events, decisions and actions that have taken place over the specified period. This approach allowed for a chronological reconstruction of events, providing a structured framework for identifying the key historical determinants that have influenced the state of crimes against humanity and national security in Ukraine. By examining primary and secondary sources, including official documents, reports, eyewitness accounts and academic literature, this method facilitated a detailed understanding of the complex dynamics at play.

The historical analysis is divided into two main phases: before and after the large-scale invasion of 2022-2023. This division not only serves as a practical means of organization, but also highlights the evolving nature of the conflict and its impact on the HRM system. By systematically documenting pre- and post-invasion events, the study provides a comprehensive view of the progression of the conflict and its humanitarian consequences.

In addition to historical analysis, we use the hermeneutic method. Its use is motivated by the need to interpret and analyze in detail key historical events and their consequences. Hermeneutics itself is defined as a specific methodological approach that includes the processes of interpreting textual materials, symbols and signs of actions that account for historical events and the social conditions in which they occur. In the context of our research, hermeneutics made it possible to conduct a critical analysis of crimes against humanity and facts of violation of human rights in the process of usurpation of national security of Ukraine.

Likewise, by using this method, all these events were analyzed from various vectors and from a broader social and political perspective. Indeed, this method allows to analyze how certain events were perceived by the population through the broadcasts of these dramatic situations through the media, direct testimonies and eyewitness accounts, demonstrating the characteristics of the interaction between the various stakeholders. Such interpretation revealed the multifaceted social, political and ethical consequences of the events that unfolded in Ukraine in 2014-2023 and their impact on the human rights and HRM system.

2. Consequences of the war in Ukraine in figures: 2014-2023

The escalation of the war in Ukraine in 2022 (State Statistics Service of Ukraine, 2023) catalyzed a mass exodus of displaced persons and refugees, marking one of the most significant population migrations in recent history, with official figures indicating that the number of people fleeing the country surpassed the one million mark and approached two million. This unprecedented forced migration was not merely a reaction to immediate threats of violence and instability, but reflected deep-seated fears of long-term insecurity and upheaval in Eastern Europe.

The sheer scale of this migration has profound implications, not only in terms of humanitarian concerns, but also in relation to the socio-economic fabric and resilience of the nation. As a substantial part of the labor force, including skilled professionals and young workers, sought refuge abroad, Ukraine faced a drastic reduction in its human capital. This depletion of the economically productive workforce poses a critical challenge to the country's ability to sustain its economy, maintain infrastructure and ensure the provision of essential services, which directly impacts its long-term recovery and stability. From a national security standpoint, the 2022 war-induced mass migration significantly complicates Ukraine's defense and homeland security strategy.

In addition, the exodus of citizens increases the vulnerability of the remaining population to external pressures and internal shocks, making the task of national reconstruction and ensuring long-term national sovereignty even more daunting. In addition, the significant and sudden exodus of personnel with skills critical to national security, particularly those necessary for the effective defense of the country (engineers, technicians, doctors), has significantly reduced the country's defense capabilities. In the area of human resource management, the implications are also significant and multifaceted (Kuzior *et al.*, 2023).

A sudden, large-scale loss of human resources requires quick action to optimize workforce planning, formulate more aggressive recruitment strategies and stimulate the development of human potential within the organization. This is especially true for companies and organizations that experienced the consequences of professional migration even before the large-scale invasion began. The events of 2022 forced the latter to quickly adapt their activities to avoid a collapse in the service and manufacturing sectors. Similarly, this problem is not limited only to the issue of outflow of personnel, but the problems of reintegration of

people leaving the conflict zone require comprehensive counseling and psychological support for an effective return to the labor market and society.

Such problems highlight the need to develop effective strategic approaches to the issue of human resources management within the framework of human rights, which can not only solve the need for human resources, but also prepare the social base to overcome the long-term consequences of these demographic shocks, while respecting the inviolability of human rights. As a result, we can state that migration caused by a large-scale invasion of the territory of Ukraine in 2022 (Eurostat, 2023) has a profound and long-term impact on national security and human resources management, while updating the relationship between social stability and economic security in the context of the struggle against adversity (Fig.2).

Figure 2. Number of people leaving the country from 2014 to 2023.

Source: Eurostat (2023) and State Statistics Service of Ukraine (2023).

The dramatic escalation of crimes against humanity in Ukraine in 2022, coinciding with the onset of a full-scale war, can be attributed to several deeply intertwined factors inherent in the nature of modern armed conflicts (State Statistics Service of Ukraine, 2023).

The large scale and intensity of military operations in various regions significantly exacerbated the vulnerability of the civilian population to violations of international law, including indiscriminate shelling, targeted attacks on residential areas, and the use of prohibited weapons. These acts not only resulted in tragic loss of life and widespread injury to the civilian population, but also led to the deliberate destruction of critical infrastructure, thus exacerbating the humanitarian crisis. The chaos of war provided fertile ground for such crimes, as the breakdown of the normal social and legal order made it difficult to enforce laws and effectively protect human rights (Fig.3).

Figure 3. Number of officially documented crimes in Ukraine as a result of the war from 2014 to 2023.

Source: State Statistics Service of Ukraine (2023).

Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine led to significant destruction of civilian infrastructure, which aggravated social problems. The catalyst for all this was also the illegal and criminal activities of the occupation authorities in the temporarily occupied territories, which created appalling social conditions for the life of local residents. Thus, there were numerous cases of crimes committed by the occupying authorities who, in the absence or inaction of local law enforcement agencies, failed to counteract them. These are acts of torture, illegal detention and other violent acts, which constitute an undeniable violation of human rights and amount to crimes against humanity. At the same time, the negative impact of the war and constant threats to life have led to social problems in the Ukrainian-controlled territories, causing an increase in crimes and violent acts.

The rise of crimes against humanity also affects international norms, posing challenges to global governance and calling into question the effectiveness and efficiency of responses to such crises (Nikolaiets et. al., 2023). The international community's struggle to address and tackle these violations in real time highlights the limitations of existing institutions and mechanisms for conflict resolution and human rights protection.

The situation in Ukraine in 2022 served as a grim reminder of the urgency for stronger international legal and humanitarian frameworks capable of preventing such atrocities. This spate of crimes against humanity not only represents a direct attack on the dignity and rights of the Ukrainian people, but also poses a challenge to the international order, highlighting the need for concerted efforts to strengthen the implementation of international law and support for nations in crisis.

History of crimes against humanity committed in Ukraine in the period 2014-2021

The period from 2014 to 2021 in Ukraine was marked by significant geopolitical turmoil, which began with the annexation of Crimea by Russia in March 2014 and, the subsequent war in eastern Ukraine, especially in the Donetsk and Luhansk regions. These events have resulted in widespread human rights abuses, violations of international law and threats to national and international security. As a result of the historical analysis, we will highlight the most significant events of this time:

1. 2014 period. In March 2014, Russia annexed Crimea following a controversial referendum. This act was widely condemned by the international community as a violation of Ukraine's sovereignty and territorial integrity, contravening the UN Charter and the 1994 Budapest Memorandum on Security Assurances. The annexation and the start of the conflict in eastern Ukraine led to forced disappearances, extrajudicial killings and torture. One notable incident was the downing of Malaysia Airlines Flight MH17 in July 2014 by a missile from territory controlled by pro-Russian separatists, killing all 298 passengers and crew (Tkachuk, 2021 and Sosnina, et. al., 2021).

2. 2015 period. Despite the agreement aimed at stopping the fighting in eastern Ukraine, violations continued, including indiscriminate shelling of civilian areas by both sides. The UN reported numerous civilian casualties and displacement of people, indicative of a disregard for the safety of civilians. Indeed, in this context:

Nearly 8,000 people have been killed in eastern Ukraine since April 2014 as a result of the ongoing conflict there, and the number of civilian casualties doubled between May and August compared to the previous three months. (United Nations, 2015, par., 3)

3. Period 2016-2017. Human rights organizations such as Human Rights Watch and Amnesty International (SWI, 2024) denounced the persecution of ethnic and religious minorities, particularly Crimean Tatars, including arbitrary arrests, enforced disappearances, and the closure of Tatar media. The conflict, characterized by trench warfare and sporadic clash-

es, resulted in civilian casualties, and both sides were accused of using prohibited weapons and failing to protect civilians.

4. Period 2018-2019. In November 2018, Russian forces seized three Ukrainian naval vessels near the Kerch Strait, claiming they had entered Russian territorial waters, prompting international condemnation. Ukraine accused Russia of attempting to interfere in its political processes, including presidential and parliamentary elections, by launching cyberattacks and spreading disinformation (Voitsikhovskiy et. al., 2022; Tataryn et. al., 2021).

5. 2020-2021 period. The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated the humanitarian situation in conflict zones, with restrictions and ongoing fighting limiting access to health care and humanitarian aid. Despite a ceasefire agreement in July 2020, sporadic fighting and ceasefire violations continued, resulting in more civilian casualties and suffering (Fig.4).

Figure 4. Examples of the most typical crimes of crimes against humanity and national security in Ukraine for the period 2014-2021.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

The crimes committed during the annexation of Crimea and the conflict in eastern Ukraine from 2014 to 2021, are of grave concern, both for their immediate human cost and their long-term impact on Europe's international norms and security. Russia's annexation of Crimea in 2014, a clear violation of international law and Ukraine's sovereignty, set a dangerous precedent for the post-World War II international order by calling into question the principle that borders cannot be changed by force. The ensuing conflict in eastern Ukraine, marked by widespread human rights abuses such as enforced disappearances, extrajudicial killings and torture, as well as indiscriminate shelling of civilian areas, resulted in thousands of deaths and millions of displaced persons.

The downing of Malaysia Airlines Flight MH17, which killed its 298 passengers and crew, is a stark reminder of the capacity of conflict to inflict tragedy on a global scale. Beyond the

immediate humanitarian crisis, these events have had a profound impact on national and international security. The conflict has led to a significant deterioration in relations between Russia and Western countries, manifested in sanctions and increased military preparedness on both sides. The internal displacement of more than 1.5 million Ukrainians has created significant humanitarian and security challenges within Ukraine and strained resources.

In addition, the annexation of Crimea and the ongoing conflict in eastern Ukraine have raised concerns about the security of nuclear materials and facilities in the region, given the violation of the Budapest Memorandum. The events of 2014-2021 highlight the complexity of modern conflicts, where territorial disputes, national sovereignty, ethnic divisions and international law intersect, posing a major challenge to global peace and security.

3. History of crimes against humanity committed in Ukraine in the period 2022-2023

Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 marked a significant escalation in a conflict that began in 2014, leading to widespread international condemnation and a humanitarian crisis. This period, which is still dragging on, witnessed a series of heinous acts that constituted crimes against humanity and gross violations of national security, profoundly affecting Ukraine's social fabric and statehood (Levy et. al., 2022; Faisal, 2021; Dulik et. al., 2023). The invasion, characterized by conventional military strikes coupled with cyber warfare, disinformation campaigns and economic coercion, highlighted a multifaceted approach to warfare aimed at destabilizing Ukraine and exerting geopolitical influence in the region.

One of the most harrowing strategies employed was the indiscriminate shelling of civilian infrastructure, including residential areas, hospitals and schools. The siege of cities such as Mariupol (between February and near the end of May 2022) is a clear example of this, as the use of heavy artillery and air strikes in densely populated areas caused a large number of civilian casualties, widespread destruction and a severe humanitarian crisis. These acts not only caused immediate loss of life and suffering, but also displaced thousands of people, with long-term socio-economic and health repercussions. The siege of Mariupol caused a severe humanitarian crisis.

The city's infrastructure was systematically targeted and destroyed, including residential buildings, hospitals and crucial facilities such as the Mariupol Theater, which was attacked on March 16, 2022, while housing hundreds of civilians. The destruction of the Azovstal steel plant, where the last redoubt of Ukrainian resistance held out, became a symbol of the city's defiance. Access to basic necessities such as food, water and medical supplies was severely restricted, leading to widespread suffering among the civilian population (Rogatinska et. al., 2023; Seleznova et. al., 2023).

During the war there were forced displacements and deportations of civilians, especially from the occupied territories. Reports of "filtration camps" where civilians were subjected to security checks and cases of forced deportations to remote areas of Russia reveal gross violations of hu-

man rights and personal freedoms. These actions were aimed at altering the demographic composition of the occupied areas, instilling fear and suppressing resistance (Yulmaz, 2023; Epel et al., 2022). The strategic occupation of Ukrainian territories, including the drive toward annexation of regions through sham referendums, posed a direct threat to Ukraine's sovereignty and territorial integrity. These occupations not only compromised Ukraine's national security landscape, but also set a precedent that defied international law and the principle of state sovereignty.

An integral part of the invasion strategy consisted of cyber-attacks against the Ukrainian government and critical infrastructure systems, along with extensive disinformation campaigns. These cyber operations were aimed at crippling the state's administrative capabilities, undermining public confidence, and spreading propaganda to justify the invasion and sow division in Ukrainian society and among its allies. The invasion profoundly affected Ukraine's human resources and personnel potential, mainly through loss of life and displacement of populations. The economic hardship, the destruction of educational facilities and the psychological trauma inflicted on several generations will have lasting repercussions on the country's development prospects and its ability to rebuild and progress after the conflict (Fig.5).

Figure 5. Examples of the most typical crimes against humanity and national security in Ukraine for the period 2022-2023.

Source: Prepared by the authors.

Conclusions and recommendations

The conflict in Ukraine, which evolved from a hybrid war initiated in 2014 to a full-scale invasion by Russia in February 2022, marks a worrying trend in today's international relations. "Hybrid warfare" combines conventional military tactics with irregular methods, cyber warfare and disinformation campaigns, seeking to destabilize and manipulate the political

and social environment of the target country without declaring open war. This strategy, used by Russia in Ukraine, exacerbated political, ethnic and social divisions, fomenting conflict and weakening Ukraine's ability to respond. The annexation of Crimea and support for separatist movements in eastern Ukraine highlight Russia's efforts to expand its influence and challenge the post-Cold War global order.

In February 2022, the conflict dramatically escalated into a full-scale invasion, exacerbating the humanitarian crisis and redefining the geopolitical landscape. This shift from hybrid tactics to open warfare has devastated Ukraine, presenting a serious challenge to international law and the principles of sovereignty and territorial integrity. Russia's intervention reflects a strategy to assert its dominance and confront the West, illustrating an ambition to redefine spheres of influence in Eastern Europe.

This protracted conflict underscores the transformation in the nature of warfare and the need for international vigilance and unity in the face of aggression that threatens global peace and order. A detailed historical analysis between 2014 and 2023 reveals the systematic commission of crimes against humanity, attacks on national security, and deterioration of the social fabric in Ukraine, exacerbated by the large-scale invasion. Ukraine's resilience highlights challenges in managing human resources and maintaining socio-economic and security stability.

In the face of the devastating effects of the Russian-driven war and the impact on Ukrainian citizens and migrants forced to seek a safe life, this article proposes recommendations in accordance with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. European and Western authorities are urged to:

- Facilitate the reception of Ukrainian migrants and simplify the procedures for their integration and active participation in the receiving societies, based on principles of humanity and administrative facilitation.
- Offer free language courses for migrants, supporting their adaptation and development in the host countries.
- Implement public policies that promote capacity building for women, children and other vulnerable groups affected by war, enabling them to pursue their life projects and preserve their cultural identities.
- This analysis warns of the potential for escalation that could directly involve NATO, posing unpredictable risks to Western civilization. Defending human rights, democracy and pluralism is crucial to preserve the fundamental values of our civilization in the face of autocracies that threaten human dignity.

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